

“Analytical Study Of Physical And Chemical Hazards On Industrial Employees ”

A RESEARCH REPORT

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National Institute Of Labour Administration Training

In partial fulfillment of the requirement

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by

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DEDICATION

I dedicate my work to.....

My teachers, for their unconditional guidance, support and personal attention that inspired me to go on my own way what I am today.....

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I thank my Allah for his blessings and support so that I could complete my work amicably.

When I write this acknowledgement, a lot of names keep on pouring into my mind who have made my otherwise tedious journey easier.

I would like to start with Sir Noor-ul-Hadi who has always guided and supported me and special thanks to Sir Dr.Akhlas for teaching and guidance regarding research work.

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the research entitled “**Analytical Study Of Physical And Chemical Hazards On Industrial Employees**” submitted by Farrukh Zaman to the National Institute Of Labour Administration Training (NILAT), Karachi for the award of the Post Graduate Diploma in Labour Administration and Industrial Welfare, is a bonafide record of the research work carried out by him under my supervision and guidance. The content of the project, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other Institute or University for the award of any other degree or diploma.

Supervisor:

**Sir Noor-Ul-Hadi
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Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Hazards in industries have been known for hundreds of years. Hazard is a term associated with a substance that is likelihood to cause an injury in a given environment or situation. Hazards in industries may be defined as any conditions produced by industries that may cause injury or death to personnel or loss of product or property.

Hazard is a situation that posses a level of threat to life, health, property or environment. Any real or potential conditions produced by industries that can cause injury or death to personnel or loss of product or property. Some of the industrial plant by the nature of their activities and the substances they use, constitute hazards.

1.2 Purpose

The purpose of this research in general is to fulfill the requirement of PGD in Labour Administration and Industrial Welfare from NILAT. The specific purpose of this research is to study the physical and chemical hazards on industrial employees of pharmaceutical sector in Pakistan.

1.3 Justification

In present scenarios hazard in industries is a major concern therefore to highlight major physical and chemical hazard in pharmaceutical industry is necessary to study.

1.4 Scope

This research is a academic research therefore its scope is limited and as far as geographical scope is concerned it is limited to pharmaceutical sector of Pakistan which I visited and sending questionnaire.

1.5 Key Terms

1.5.1 Physical Hazard

A physical hazard is an agent, fact or circumstance that can cause harm if exposed. Examples include noise, vibration, temperature extremes (hot or cold) and radiation.

1.5.2 Chemical Hazard

A chemical hazard is a type of hazard that caused by exposure to chemicals in the workplace that can cause acute or long term detrimental health effects.

1.6 Research Methodology

Quantitative type of research methodology is used in this research. For this, a questionnaire is designed to assess physical and chemical hazard in pharmaceutical and auto industry workplace. Three options

are given in each eleven questions. Three Companies (2 Pharmaceuticals and 1 Auto) are Sample and target respondents are Environment Health Safety (EHS) department representatives.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

Chemical hazards are a major occupational health and safety (OHS) issue in pharmaceutical industry. These chemical substances can enter the unprotected body by inhalation, skin absorption, ingestion or through a puncture wound (injection).

Little is known about the health risks of working in the pharmaceutical industry. On the surface the industry looks clean. The production of medicinal demand a carefully maintained and sterile working environment and the white lab coats worn by workers add to the illusion of safety. The appearances are deceptive through producing drugs and other medicinal may involve exposure to toxic industrial chemicals and while the finished product may be life saving medications for sick people they can be dangerous to healthy workers who are inhaling or absorbing them during the production process.[1]

2.1 Types of chemical Hazards

Chemical hazards are toxic, corrosive, irritant, carcinogenic, flammable, and mutagenic .

According to workplace hazardous materials information, chemical hazards are classified as : [2]

Class A

- Compressed gas.
- Dissolved gas or liquefied gas.

Class B [Figure 1]

- Flammable gases.
- Flammable and combustible liquids.
- Flammable solid.
- Flammable aerosols.
- Reactive flammable material.

Class C

- Oxidizing materials - oxidizer and organic peroxide.
- Oxidizer: Chlorates, nitric oxide, peroxides, permanganates, perchlorates, nitrites, nitrates, and easily oxidize metal powder.
- Organic peroxide: Tetra hydro furan, diethyl ether, dioxane, and methyl isobutyl ether.

Class D

- Poisonous and infectious materials.
- e.g.: Cyanides, tea salts, and asbestos.

Class E

- Corrosive materials.
- e.g.: Inorganic acids and bases, hydrogen fluoride.

Class F

- Dangerous reactive materials.
- e.g.: Ethylene dioxide, organic azides, Na, Li, Ca.

- Pyrophosphoric materials.
e.g.: White phosphorous, diethyl aluminum chloride, and lithium.[3,4]

Carcinogens

The identification of carcinogenic agents was based on the IARC classification and corresponding IARC monographs.[5,6] Only agents belonging to Group 1 were considered, i.e., agents for which there is sufficient evidence of carcinogenicity in humans, and therefore, a causal relationship between agent and increased incidence of malignant neoplasms has been established. The estimates of the number of specific exposures of a worker were taken from the database carcinogens exposure.[7].These estimates correspond to the exposure period 1990–1993 across 55 industrial sectors for the EU-15 countries.[7,8]

2.2 EFFECTS OF CHEMICALS EXPOSURE ON HUMAN BODY

- Skin burn,
- Ache,
- Anthrax,
- Ulcer in hand, nose, etc.
- Cancer,
- Irritation on windpipe,
- Many chemicals can cause severe burns, if they come in contact with living tissue,

2.3 Chemical Hazards Can Enter and Harm the Body by Four Main Routes

- Absorption through the skin;
- Inhalation;
- Injection; and
- Ingestion.[20]

2.4 DIFFERENT WAYS OF CHEMICAL HAZARDS CAUSE HARM

- Catching fire.
- Explosive or reactive.
- Corrosive.
- Irritant.
- Causing chronic organ damage over time.
- Causing an allergic reaction.
- Causing genetic or reproductive harm.[20]

The effects of exposure not only depend on the chemical, its concentration, route of entry, and duration of exposure, but may also be influenced by personal factors such as the individual's smoking habits, alcohol consumption, medication use, nutrition, age, and sex.

An important exposure route of concern at a hazardous waste site is inhalation. The lungs are extremely vulnerable to chemical agents. Even substances that do not directly affect the lungs may pass through lung tissue into the bloodstream, where they are transported to other vulnerable areas of the body. Some toxic chemicals present in the atmosphere may not be detected by human senses, i.e., they may be colorless, odorless, and their toxic effects may not produce any immediate symptoms. Respiratory

protection is, therefore, extremely important if 2-3 there is a possibility that the work-site atmosphere may contain such hazardous substances. Chemicals can also enter the respiratory tract through punctured eardrums. Direct contact of the skin and eyes by hazardous substances is another important route of exposure. Some chemicals directly injure the skin. Some pass through the skin into the bloodstream where they are transported to vulnerable organs. Skin absorption is enhanced by abrasions, cuts, heat, and moisture. The eye is particularly vulnerable because airborne chemicals can dissolve in its moist surface and be carried to the rest of the body through the bloodstream (capillaries are very close to the surface of the eye). Wearing protective equipment, not using contact lenses in contaminated atmospheres (since they may trap chemicals against the eye surface), keeping hands away from the face, and minimize contact with liquid and solid chemicals can help protect against skin and eye contact.[9]

Although ingestion should be the least significant route of exposure at a site, it is important to be aware of how this type of exposure can occur. Deliberate ingestion of chemicals is unlikely, however, personal habits such as chewing gum or tobacco, drinking, eating, smoking cigarettes, and applying cosmetics on site may provide a route of entry for chemicals.[20]

The last primary route of chemical exposure is injection, whereby chemicals are introduced into the body through puncture wounds (for example, by stepping or tripping and falling onto contaminated sharp objects). Wearing safety shoes, avoiding physical hazards, and taking common-sense precautions are important protective measures against injection.[20]

2.5 Physical hazards

Physical hazards include surroundings of the workers such as heat, cold, loud noise, poor lighting, poor ventilation, vibration, electricity and radiations. Excessive heat from ovens & furnaces may lead to fatigue, prickly heat, cramps, syncope and heat

2.5.1 Types Of Physical Hazards

- Mechanical hazards
- Electrical Hazards
- Thermal Hazards
- Noise Hazards
- Vibration Hazards
- Ionizing Radiation
- Non-Ionizing Radiation
- Illumination (Light) Hazards

Mechanical Hazards

It occurs due to exertion of mechanical force on the workers body or parts of machinery beyond the limit that the system can endure. It produces stress on musculoskeletal system. This stress can be result of a blow, a constant pulling or a pushing on the body structure. Fatigue is an indication of such kind of stresses. Common examples of the hazards presented in the industrial environment are unguarded moving parts of the machinery, improper seating or standing arrangements.

Electrical Hazards

These hazard can be divided into following five categories:

- Shock to personnel
- Ignition of combustible (or explosive) material
- Overheating and damage to equipment or burns
- Electrical explosions
- Inadvertent activation of equipment

Common examples present in industry are

- Naked wires
- Un-insulated equipment
- Broken wires

Thermal Hazards

Exposure to extreme heat, extreme cold or rapid change in temperature

High rate of perspiration cause loss of salt

Dehydration result in loss of body water.

Prolonged exposure leads to fatigue

Due to widening of pores opening, increase the absorption rate of any toxic matter present in the environment.

Noise Hazards

Unwanted sound is noise. Noise intensity and period of exposure are the main factors.

Vibration Hazards

Vibration originates from mechanical motion. Vibration produces shaking of the body or parts of body.

There two types of vibration (a) Whole body vibration (b)Segmental vibration

Ionizing Radiation

Ionizing radiation includes alpha, beta, gamma and X-ray. Effects bone marrow and blood, eyes, skin, digestive system, nervous system, hairs and organs like kidney, liver and heart which result in chronic effect like carcinogenic and gene-damaging effects.

Non-Ionizing Radiation

It includes ultraviolet, infrared, laser and microwave rays.

Illumination

Inadequate illumination cause eye strain, increase chances of error and reduce efficiency. Glares sometimes cause temporary blindness resulting in an accident. From different kind of work the illumination level ranges from 300 to 1500 LUX.

Chapter 3 Data Analysis

Figure 1

All three companies namely GSK, Agri Autos and Ferozsions had noise dosimeter present at their workplace.

Figure 2

Both GSK and Ferozsions had noise level of 95 dB however Agri Autos had noise level above 95 dB.

Figure 3

In GSK and Agri Autos the minimum illumination level were 400 LUX while in Ferozsos the minimum illumination level was below 400 LUX.

Figure 4

All the three companies namely GSK, Agri Autos and Ferozsos had 500 cft space available at their workplace.

Figure 5

The nature of chemical exposure at workplace in all three companies were inhalation.

Figure 6

In all three companies namely GSK, Agri Autos and Ferozsos machineries were properly fenced.

Figure 7

In GSK and Ferozsos the level of chemical exposure were minimum threshold values however in Agri Autos the level of chemical exposure is maximum threshold values.

Figure 8

All the three companies namely GSK, Agri Autos and Ferozsos medically examined and inoculate their workers.

Figure 9

In all three companies namely GSK, Agri Autos and Ferozsos the compensation paid to affected workers or dependent of deceased workers.

Figure 10

In GSK the frequency of fire incident was once in a year however in Agri Autos and Ferozsos the frequency were once in years.

Figure 11

The GSK had less than 5% occupational diseased workers however Agri Autos had less than 2% occupational diseased workers while ferozsos had less than 1 % occupational diseased workers.

Chapter 4 Conclusion and Recommendation

4.1 Conclusion:

By analysis, it was found that all the three companies namely; GSK, Agri Autos and Ferozsos had satisfactory measures to monitor and control Physical and Chemical hazards at their workplace.

However, the parameters selected for questionnaire are not necessary cover all the things of physical and chemical hazards at workplace.

Moreover, the hazards not present in these companies may be present in other companies of same nature companies.

With limited number of time the data collected could not be verified for accuracy.

4.2 Recommendation From Research:

As we have analyzed the physical and chemical hazards at workplace the area identified for improvement is to reduce chemical exposure tend to zero by making effective monitoring of exposure limits and periodically inspection of concerned sensitive workplace areas.

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Appendix:

Questionnaire For Research Study Of Topic

“ Analytical Study Of Physical & Chemical Hazards On Industrial Worker”

Name of Factory/ Organization : _____

Q.1 Is there any noise dosimeter present at concern area of workplace?

(a) Yes (b) No (c) Not Yet

Q.2 If indicator present then what is the measured maximum noise level?

(a) Below 95 db (b) 95 db (c) Above 95 db

Q.3 What is the minimum measured illumination level?

(a) Below 400 LUX (b) 400 LUX (c) Above 400 LUX

Q.4 Is there space 500 Cft available / provided for working at work place?

(a) Yes (b) No (c) Not measured

Q.5 What is the common nature of chemical exposure at your workplace?

(a) Inhale (b) Ingest (c) Skin Contact

Q.6 Are moving parts of machineries properly guided or fenced?

(a) Cover (b) Not Cover (c) Semi –cover

Q.7 What is the monitor level of chemical exposure?

(a) Minimum Threshold Limit values (b) Maximum Threshold limit values (c) In between minimum & maximum limit values

Q.8 Are the workers medically examined & inoculated against epidemic diseases?

(a) Yes (b) No (c) Seldomly

Q.9 Whether compensation was paid to the relevant workers or dependent of diseased workers/ affected workers?

(a)Yes (b) No (c) Rarely

Q.10 What is the frequency of fire incident?

(a) Once in a year (b) Once in years (c) In Six month

Q.11 What is the percentage of Occupational diseased workers?

(a) Less than 5 % (b) Less than 2 % (c) Less than 1%